

BORN FOR THIS: BUILDING A BRAND IDENTITY
SENIOR HONORS PROJECT

By

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ABSTRACT

In our current society, where identity and personhood are under attack, Joan of Arc proves to be an excellent role model by living a life of individuality. Jeanne d’Arc, commonly known as Joan of Arc, was a young peasant who lived in France during the 100 Years’ War. She became a military leader at seventeen and lifted the siege of Orleans, a pivotal victory during the war. “I am not afraid; I was born for this” is a quote attributed to Joan because of her unwavering bravery and belief in her calling. She was firm in her womanhood and courageous in her military endeavors, gaining the respect of everyone around her and still everyone today. *Born for This* brand promotes self-confidence in a person’s unique personhood, like Joan of Arc. Its mission is to promote that through their individual, unrepeatable, unique calling, each and every person is made for greatness. *Born for This* believes that every person has the capability for greatness within them; it just needs to be lived out. The brand promotes confidence and internal fortitude with merchandise focusing on Joan of Arc’s strength in her personhood. The merchandise will include shirts, totes, stickers, and poster designs with unique illustrations of Joan’s character that remind consumers of the greatness within themselves.

KEYWORDS: brand identity, Joan of Arc, personhood, identity, merchandise

INTRODUCTION

Joan of Arc has always been the person I have looked up to. Her courage, her fortitude, and her zeal were traits that I found so admirable. When I was brainstorming ideas back in my sophomore year of college for my senior honors project, doing something related to my career was the most obvious route. So, this project started with a straightforward idea: to create a strong portfolio project that covers brand identity, which I believe is vital in a successful graphic designer's portfolio. Any type of business needs strong branding along with a strong mission statement. My core values are integrity, benevolence, excellence, and dependability, which I want to focus on in my brand. I was immediately reminded of Joan of Arc's integrity, excellence, and dependability. I thought of creating a brand based on a paraphrase of her quote, "I am not afraid; I was born for this." Throughout its creation, my project evolved into something more than just a branding project on Joan of Arc. It turned into a movement that advocates for the greatness of every individual. I created an original logo, color scheme, illustrations, business cards, and merchandise such as shirts, totes, and postcards that fit my brand's core values. This paper serves as a documentation and step-by-step process behind the creation of *Born for This* apparel, starting with the ideation, development, and then execution of the project.

RESEARCH AND IDEATION

The first step in my project was to research Joan of Arc. Over the summer of 2023, I read *Joan of Arc* by Lucy Foster Madison and *Personal Recollections of Joan of Arc* by Mark Twain to learn more about Joan and her life. My primary source of information while conducting research and collecting specific information on Joan of Arc was *The Life of Joan of Arc* by Anatole France, translated by Winifred Stephens. Joan of Arc, French name Jeanne d'Arc, was

born to Jacques d'Arc and Isabelle Romée in 1412 in the village of Domremy, France (France). She lived a peaceful childhood with her four siblings until her village was attacked when she was thirteen years old during the Hundred Years' War (France). Also, at thirteen, Joan began receiving visions of Saints Michael the Archangel, Margaret of Antioch, and Catherine of Alexandria (France). In her visions, the saints urged her to leave her village and go to France, to which Joan replied that she was just a poor girl and did not know how to ride (France). For three years, Joan ignored her visions until she finally convinced her older cousin, Durand Lassois, to take her to see Robert de Baudricourt, the captain of the royal garrison, under the guise of going to see her cousin (Twain, 50). Baudricourt refused Joan at first since she was just a peasant girl. Still, after seeing how she influenced those around her through her integrity and sincerity, he conceded a year later. He gave her a horse and six escorts to see the Dauphin (France). Before her departure, Joan cut her hair to the length of a page boy and donned men's clothing which she wore for the rest of her life (Twain 81). Finally, at age seventeen, Joan could speak to the Dauphin about her visions. She promised to save France with her military leadership and allow him to be crowned King Charles VII of France. The Dauphin had her examined and tested to see if she was truthful and, ultimately, granted Joan permission to lead an army to Orleans (Twain 102). The word that a young maiden had decided to lead an army to retake Orleans stirred hope and life back into the French people. Through her leadership and valor, on May 8, 1429, Joan lifted the siege of Orleans just as she promised and changed France's fate in the war (Twain, 127). After King Charles VII's coronation, Joan wished to return to her family and live a peaceful village life. However, the King asked her to lead the French army to Paris, and Joan obeyed. In the battle at Paris, Joan was wounded, and the French failed to take Paris, but she still urged her soldiers on and gallantly fought in the war until they dragged her off the battlefield

(Twain, 158). The royal court doubted her capabilities after her defeat in Paris and other campaigns. Still, it later allowed her to lead a small group of men to lift the siege of Siege of Compiègne, where she was captured by the Burgundian army (France). The English bought her for a ransom price and then placed her on trial for heresy and blasphemy (Twain, 176). Joan's public hearings lasted six days but did not conclude because she answered truthfully and without fault (Twain, 185). Joan was coerced to renounce her beliefs and her values to escape burning at the stake, and she complied, but then renounced her renouncement of her beliefs and was sentenced to death for heresy (France). On May 30, 1431, at age eighteen, Joan was burned at the stake.

Every brand's name should immediately draw interest, be easy to remember, be unique, and be vetted ("The Complete Step by Step"). Using my core values of integrity and fortitude, the mission statement that I plan to promote with my brand is that "through their individual, unrepeatable, unique calling, each and every person is made for greatness and to make a difference." When Joan was journeying to visit the Dauphin, villagers asked her if she was afraid before leaving. Still, Joan confidently answered, "I am not afraid of enemy soldiers. My path is safe before me... I was born for this purpose" (Twain, 81). This quote has been paraphrased into "I am not afraid; I was born for this" over the years and has been attributed to Joan of Arc because it exudes her core values of bravery, fortitude, and integrity. Thus, the name *Born for This* was chosen for my brand.

To combine my two goals of having a solid portfolio project along with a brand that promoted a message that aligned with my values, having a set list of deliverables and expectations helped me stay on track. At the beginning of my project, I set out to create and design a logo, original typeface, color scheme, design system, and final presentation box that

held shirts, totes, posters, stickers, and business cards. The first half of the project would be more technical and portfolio-based, while the second half would be more consumer and business-based. The shirt, tote, poster, and sticker designs would all feature images of Joan of Arc that depicted her most prominent character traits. Customers wear these items as a reminder of their unique personhood and that they are capable of greatness and making a difference, just as Joan does. I researched art movements during Joan's lifetime and decided to reference the Art Nouveau, Pre-Raphaelite, and Romantic art styles that convey beauty and strength in the designs. I also researched medieval blackletter typefaces with flourishes. In addition, calligraphic, textured fonts from old manuscripts and Joan's signature are what I referenced when creating the logo for the brand. Finally, for the color scheme and feel of the brand, I chose hues that were brown and beige earthy toned to emulate a grounded aesthetic and a muted red and blue to reference the colors of the French flag.

After researching Joan's life and potential brand aesthetics, I began researching printing services. My initial research led me to choose *Esty* as my storefront. *Esty* is a "global marketplace for unique and creative goods" and is the first choice for most artists looking to sell their work ("About Esty"). However, when selling on *Esty*, the seller oversees the supply and distribution of their products. As a full-time college student, I did not have the funds and time to buy my products in bulk and then distribute them, so I began searching for a printing service that did. Through my research, I discovered *Bonfire*, a small printing company based in Richmond, Virginia, where the seller can "focus on connecting" while *Bonfire* manages orders behind the scenes ("About Bonfire"). At *Bonfire*, sellers can start campaigns where a product is for sale for a certain number of days and then printed and distributed to customers when the campaign is over. *Bonfire* campaigns may range from two to twenty-one days, with orders bringing print the

day after it closes. My main selling point for *Bonfire* was the ability to start and sell multiple campaigns simultaneously while managing them all under one storefront, making it easier for the consumer. *Bonfire* proved to be an excellent printing service for my needs. However, it only sold apparel products and not other items such as stickers or postcards. Due to its speed and reliance, I chose the Digital Printing Services (DPS) at California State University, Fullerton, for my printed material.

The final research component of my project was studying what brand building entailed. At the beginning of my junior year, I had not yet created a branding guide, so I began researching what was required in a brand identity system. Common elements I saw were firm logos that could be translated into different ratios, core values conceptualized into repeating visual elements, and a cohesive color scheme used across the brand's guide. One brand that I looked to for inspiration in branding was *Kréshta Bajaj*, an Indian contemporary luxury brand based in Mumbai, India, whose muse is a "fiercely feminine woman who embraces all her moods" ("About Us"). Their brand book, designed by Ahsar Damani, stood out because they promoted their brand with images and examples of their work and their mission statement to display the marriage between inspiration and product. The second brand guide that I referenced was *The Style Room's Digital Style Guide*. *The Style Room*, a curated fashion shopping company within Zappos, included a detailed breakdown of their logo with explanations, various iterations, and detailed ratio aspects, highlighting the importance of a clean and intentional logo for my brand. In addition to a strong identity system, consistent social media presence and promotions are also necessary to have a successful brand. *Baritus Catholic Illustrations*, *Just Love Prints*, and *Not Yet Home* are three small business owners that successfully promote their creative shops by keeping a solid social media presence and engaging with their followers through polls,

comments, and story reshares. In addition to follower interaction, my research showed that posts that utilized Instagram Reels and video/audio content received more likes and views than regular posts (“Posts”).

DEVELOPMENT AND METHODOLOGY

I decided to implement elements of Joan’s coat of arms for my logo. Joan had a coat of arms gifted to her family and brothers by the Dauphin that depicted a crown atop an upright sword, two fleurs-de-lis on either side (France). I wanted to include the fleur-de-lis in the logo to symbolize her French roots and use the sword and crown to represent Joan’s unique calling and astute nature. The typeface chosen for the logos was hand-lettered to reference the black letter type used in the 1300s. I took these elements from her coat of arms and my hand-lettered type to create the primary logo in a 1:1 ratio (see Figure 1.1). I then translated the primary logo into a secondary logo with a horizontal 3:2 ratio (see Figure 1.2). Then, I created a logo mark using the visual elements of the fleur-de-lis, crown, and sword in a vertical line that may serve as a watermark (see Figure 1.3).

After creating the logo, I began working on my first product design. My idea for the first product design was to create a more illustrative artwork that would be used on shirts, totes, and stickers. I started with my loose sketches of Joan in Procreate and then worked to tighten my linework and proportions. Since I wanted to create an artwork that could be used on different mediums, I wanted to create an image that could translate well onto larger surfaces like the back of a shirt or a smaller item like a postcard. In the early stages of the shirt creation, I placed my designs on a shirt mockup on Canva to get an overall idea of its layout. I also wanted my work to have a rustic, linocut appearance, like old artwork, but with a more contemporary composition. I

sketched out different ideas of Joan riding to war, waving her flag, or receiving visions, but I chose the sketch that depicted her at peace during her execution. Although she was tied to a stake and was not executed in her military outfit, I decided to draw her in her suit of armor, holding a flag and sword, to represent her unwavering courage and belief in her calling even at death's door. I depicted her eyes closed and youthful and serene face to represent her young age and calmness, making her a great military leader in history. To push the concept of individuality, I drew an arched frame around Joan and the flames but broke the border with the flag and some flames to symbolize Joan's ability to step out of established societal rules of conduct to reach her goals. I then colorized my illustration in the CMYK color profile with the colors I had chosen from my research for the brand and uploaded them to my laptop. After uploading them to my computer, I opened my illustrations in Adobe Illustrator and created different shirt design layouts. The layout I chose to finalize was the design where I placed the words "I am not afraid" under the illustration while keeping the symbols of the sword, crown, and fleur-de-lis balanced around it (see Figures 2.1 and 2.2).

The last design I needed to create was the second shirt design. My idea for this design was a more text-based design with the phrase, "born for this." I sketched out the ideas for this design in Procreate on my iPad and selected the one that stood out. I decided to finalize the design that reiterated the phrase three times as if it were a mantra. The base typeface I chose for the text designs was Gryphius MVB. I then converted my text to outlines and simplified the paths to create a smoother appearance. I then placed two fleurs-de-lis on either side of the design as an homage to the two found on Joan's Coat of Arms. I then changed each iteration's text color to create a gradient with different colors as a symbol of each person's unique calling that is different from the people around them (see Figure 3.0).

After revising and finalizing the designs, it was time to apply them to merchandise to be sold and printed. On *Bonfire*, I selected the Classic Unisex Tees in Sand and Dark Chocolate colors to place my designs on. Although most printing services have an area where the artwork must fit in the mockup for it to be fully printed, fine adjustments to the positioning, sizing, and attention to detail are crucial to a great design. I built each merchandise listing off the previous one to remain cohesive to the consumer. For the illustrated shirt design, I chose to keep a more simplified line art design on the back of a beige-colored shirt (see Figure 5.2) and then a colorized version of the illustration on the back of a beige and dark brown colored shirt (see figures 5.3 and 6.2). The front of the illustrated shirt stayed consistent in layout across the different colored shirts and illustration styles, as I kept the primary logo in the front left corner (see Figures 5.1 and 6.1). For the text-based shirt design, I placed the design in the front center of the shirt, the secondary logo in the back center, and applied the layout to both the beige and dark brown shirts (see Figures 7.1-7.4). I created the tote bag designs with two options: the illustrated or text-based design on the front and the secondary logo on the back (see figures 8.1-8.3). Finally, the postcards were designed by placing the colored illustration (see Figure 2.2) on a flat brown background, stickers were die cuts of the primary logo and colored illustrations, and business cards were designed using the secondary logo and a QR code to the storefront (see figures 4.1 and 4.2).

After finalizing the designs, my next step was setting up print orders, my virtual storefront, and promoting my brand. I sample-printed my shirt designs from *Bonfire* and ordered prints of the postcards and business cards from DPS. My prints came back successfully from DPS, except one of my shirt designs came back incorrectly from *Bonfire*. A challenge I faced was communicating with them about my issue over their live chat and email since they did not

have a phone number through which to speak. However, over a couple of days, my problem was resolved as a misprint on their end, and they offered to send me a replacement. After overcoming this print challenge, I set up my storefront and posted promotional content to my brand's Instagram account. After initially researching social media accounts and promoting practices, I decided that posting an Instagram reel would attract the most viewers. Then, I posted every other day with a series of who, what, where, and when posts that described my project, who it was based on, and where and when my products would be available.

CONCLUSION

Finally, through detailed and strenuous ideation, development, and execution, my senior honors project, *Born for This: Building a Brand Identity*, came to a successful close. *Born for This* is meant to inspire, empower, and encourage its consumers to embrace their individuality and personhood, focusing on the life of Joan of Arc and how she lived bravely and authentically. The mission statement that through their individual, unrepeatably, unique calling, each and every person is made for greatness was an excellent foundation for building a solid brand identity. The different products, such as shirts, postcards, and stickers, will inspire confidence in its consumers through its designs. The brand identity I established will be a great portfolio piece and highlight what I am capable of as a designer. I learned many valuable lessons on business practices and Joan of Arc through research that will help me in my future career. However, the biggest lesson I learned through the creation of *Born for This* is that I, just like Joan of Arc, am also made for greatness and to make a difference.

Figure 1.1

Figure 1.2

Figure 1.3

i am not afraid

Figure 2.1

i am not afraid

Figure 2.2

born for this
✦ *born for this* ✦
born for this

Figure 3.0

Figure 4.1

Figure 4.2

Figure 5.1

Figure 5.2

Figure 5.3

Figure 6.1

Figure 6.2

Figure 7.1

Figure 7.2

Figure 7.3

Figure 7.4

Figure 8.1

Figure 8.2

Figure 8.3

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